

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF PROGRESSIVE CRUSHING OF PULTRUDED COMPOSITE TUBES UNDER AXIAL BLAST LOAD

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SUMMARY

A numerical investigation was carried out to evaluate the response of pultruded composite tubes, made of polyvinylester matrix reinforced uni-directionally with glass fibers, to axial blast loading. A full scaled model of the specimen was developed to simulate the experiments using LS_DYNA3D. The finite element solutions were validated using experimental data that was published by [1]. Good correlation, based on transmitted impulse by the explosive and crushed distance of the composite tube, was obtained between the finite element simulations and experiments.

Keywords: Blast Load, Pultruded Tube, Progressive Crushing, Finite Element

INTRODUCTION

Tubular structures are very good energy absorbers because of their ability to absorbing energy very effectively during impact events[2, 3]. With the ever-increasing demand for light weight energy absorbers, composite tubes have become more attractive because of their numerous damage mechanisms such as delamination, matrix cracking, fiber cracking and debonding of the fibers. Several researchers have carried out experimental and numerical studies on the crushing characteristics of composite tubes and its capabilities as energy absorbers [4-9]. Hitherto, most of these studies have concentrated on quasi-static or dynamic impact loading of these structures for crashworthiness applications. With the increasing terrorist threat the need to investigate the energy absorbing capabilities of the tubular structures subjected to load in the blasting regime has become more important. Carrying out experiments of such nature is not always

readily accessible. As an alternative, finite element codes can help to characterize the response of these structures subjected to such extreme loading conditions and provide better insights into the failing mechanisms that are not physically possible to analyze.

A large number of experimental and theoretical studies focus on the failure and crashworthiness of composite tubes: either purely numerical [10]; trying to study various characteristics of the tubes, or purely experimental [11-13]; studying the types of failure and the energy absorption mechanisms, or both numerical-experimental; [14, 15] studying the specific energy absorption and peak forces trying to compare the two types of data and correlate them with the factors that affect the numerical modeling and the various characteristics of the tubes[15].

Numerous authors have carried out work to investigate blast loads resulting from the detonation of high explosive [16-21]. When high explosive is detonated an inward wave is generated in the explosive material, at the same time, a shock wave moves through the air medium and interact with any structures in its path. The resulting flow is very complex and involves several physical phenomena [21, 22]. Numerical simulations help to minimize the number of costly tests required and also help to interpret test results that cannot be captured easily during an experiment. The simulation of the blast load is also very difficult for classical numerical methods [23]. Recently, the development of Eulerian Multi-material formulations, has provided an alternative to simulate high explosive phenomena [24, 25], for close range explosions. Nevertheless, the response of simple structures, such as plates, beams and shells, to blast loading have been extensively carried out to understand the large permanent ductile deformation and rupture of these structures both experimentally and numerically[17-21].

This paper presents the numerical investigation of pultruded composite tubes subjected to axial blast loads using LS-DYNA. The finite element model is validated using previous experiments published by [1].

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Modelling the Specimen

The composite tubes, made of pultruded glass fiber reinforced with epoxy vinyl ester matrix, were modeled with two layers of Belyschko-Tsay quadrilateral shell elements. The elements were located at the mid-plane of the one half of the thickness of the tube and they were separated by a small gap equal to the average thickness of the two layers. The interaction between the two layers was configured by contact algorithms. Each layer is modeled as two laminas of 0° orientation by two integration points each, evenly distributed through the thickness. The impacted edge was cut in a tulip type trigger [9, 11] at a 45° angle as shown in Figure 1. The length of the specimens was 100mm, with outer diameter of 25.4mm and inner diameter 21.3mm.

At the impact end, the striking mass, a circular steel disc, is placed in contact with the tube with the explosive place at a stand-off distance of 13mm from the disk, as in the experimental set-up. The striking mass was modeled with 660 brick elements. The explosive and a cuboid of air surrounding the experiment were modeled with 8-node brick elements which have no shear strength [23]. The assembly of the finite element model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. The triggering mechanism on one edge of the tube.

Figure 2. Schematic showing the model used for the finite element simulation.

Modelling the Material

The constitutive material model 54 was selected to model the pultruded composite tube. Material model 54 has the option of using either the Tsai –Wu failure or the Chang-Chang failure criterion. In this case the Chang-Chang criterion is used which is a modification of Hashin criterion to account for non linear shear stress-strain behavior [10]. According to this model, if fiber breakage and/or fiber matrix shear failure occurs in a lamina, both the lamina’s transverse modulus and minor Poisson’s ratio are reduced to zero. If matrix failure occurs then the transverse modulus and minor Poisson’s ratio are reduced to zero, while the longitudinal modulus and shear remain unchanged. The material properties, taken from literature [26], are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties of the pultruded profile.

Glass Fiber/Polyester pultruded profile								
E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	ν_{xy}	G_{xy}	σ_{xxT} (MPa)	σ_{yyT} (MPa)	σ_{xxC} (MPa)	σ_{yyC} (MPa)	τ_{xy} (MPa)
31.2	9.36	0.29	3.2	483	34.9	409	92.2	73.3

The striking mass is modeled using the material model 03 Plastic Kinematic with the mild steel properties.

Table 2. Material Properties of the striking mass.

Mild Steel			
E _o (GPa)	ν	ρ _o (kg/mm ³)	σ _v (GPa)
210	0.3	7.85e-06	0.6

Modelling the Boundary Conditions

Non-reflecting boundaries were applied around the elements of air and the non-impact end of the tube was fixed. Between the two layers of the tube, *AUTOMATIC SURFACE TO SURFACE TIEBREAK was applied to tie the layers using the transverse strength and the shear strength of the material model of the tube. The contact algorithm accounts for both normal and shear forces in the interface. Between the tube and the striking mass the command *AUTOMATIC ONE WAY SURFACE TO SURFACE was used, and a coefficient of friction of 0.2 (mild steel – polyester) is applied for the specific contact.

Modelling the load

In the experiments, the impulsive load was created by detonating plastic explosive PE4 (commonly known as C4) in a similar fashion to that was used in previous experimental investigation [18-20]. A free striking mass, made of mild steel, 108g in mass and 25mm in diameter, was centrally loaded with the plastic explosive (PE4). Three different charge masses, 5, 9 and 13g, were used at a stand-off distance of 13mm from the striking mass to provide different impulses.

In the finite element model, an Eulerian multi-material formulation is applied to modeling the air-explosive and tube interactions. Air and explosive are described by two equations of state given by Eqs 1 and 2.

For air, density, pressure cut-off and viscosity coefficient are defined. The viscosity and pressure cut-off are set to zero, because pressure cannot be negative and the viscosity forces are negligible. The ideal gas law (gamma law) is used as the equation of state for air. This polytropic equation of state is given by considering the general linear polynomial equation of state [23]:

$$p = C_0 + C_1\mu + C_2\mu^2 + C_3\mu^3 + E(C_4 + C_5\mu + C_6\mu^2) \quad (1)$$

For ideal gas, equation 1 can be reduced using appropriate coefficients ($C_0 = C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_6 = 0$, $C_4 = C_5 = \gamma - 1$), $p = (\gamma - 1)\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}E$, ρ and ρ_0 are the current and initial densities of air, E is the specific internal energy and γ is the polytropic ratio of specific heats.

For the explosive and its detonating products, the Jones–Wilkins–Lee (JWL) equation of state (EOS) relating energy, pressure and density is applied. While there are various types of EOS describing the state of the detonation products, the JWL EOS is widely used because of its simplicity. The definition of the JWL equation of state can start from an isentropic form, namely:

$$p_s = A \exp(-R_1 V) + B \exp(-R_2 V) + C V^{-(\omega+1)} \quad (2)$$

where p is the pressure and the subscript “s” denotes reference to isentropic compression or expansion. A , B , R_1 , R_2 and x are constants.

Table 3. Parameters of air [23].

Air		
γ	$E_0(\text{GPa})$	$\rho_0(\text{kg/mm}^3)$
1.4	2.5e-04	1.29e-09

Table 4. Parameters of PE-4 [23].

PE-4								
$A(\text{GPa})$	$B(\text{GPa})$	R_1	R_2	$E(\text{GPa})$	ω	$V_d(\text{mm/msec})$	$\rho(\text{kg/mm}^3)$	$p_{CJ}(\text{GPa})$
589.1553	13.75	4.5	1.5	8.699	0.32	8040	1.601e-06	28.1

RESULTS

Experimental Results

The failed specimens as observed from the experiments are shown in Figure 3. Debonding and delamination mechanism are observed where the tubes failed from impact end. In the axial direction the tubes failed in such a way that they petalled like a flower would open up when blossom with the fibers scattering.

Figure 3. The failed specimens after 5, 9 and 13 g of C4 [19].

Table 5. Experimental results

Mass of Explosive (g)	Crushed Distance (mm)	Impulse (Ns)
5	21.8	6.82
9	41	10.76
13	45.5	14.39

Numerical Results

The axial explosive response of the tubes is evaluated by means of force-time and energy absorption for the three different explosive masses. The results are shown in Table 6 and Figure 4. As expected with an increase of the explosive mass increases the

impulse and the kinetic energy of the striking mass and consequently the crushed distance of the tube.

Table 6. Summary of finite element simulation results

	Crushed Distance (mm)	Impulse (Ns)	Peak Force (kN)	Kinetic Energy (J)
5g	12.6	4.2	10.2	82.14
9g	22.7	7.4	21.1	247.05
13g	44.1	10.8	32.4	532.86

a) Tube subjected to 5g of explosive

b) Tube subjected to 9g of explosive

c) Tube subjected to 13g of explosive

Figure 4. The transient response of the tubes for a) 5g, b) 9g and c) 13g.

The tube starts to fold at the triggering mechanism with delamination occurring between layers as a result of the tie break contact. Stress concentration is observed in the corners of the edge as it is indicated in Figure 4a, which leads to erosion of the elements around that area. Qualitatively, the failure pattern is similar with the experimental where part of the wall of the tube folds inwards and part of the tube folds outwards. The layers are also observed to rupture along the length off the tube during the progressive crushing.

Figure 5 shows force vs. crushed distance as typically observed for tubular structures subjected to axial impact loading. Initially, the crushed force is similar for all tubes irrespective of charge mass, thereafter increases with increasing charge mass – due to the densification of the matrix debris and the debonded fibers. As the charge mass is increased higher crushed distance is observed. The absorbed energy due to failure during the progressive crushing is shown in Figure 6. The increase of the charge mass leads to an increase in the impulse, as expected.

A comparison between experimental and numerical data for crushed distance and impulse is shown in Figure 7(a) and Figure 7(b) respectively. Slight variation is observed for the crushed distance. In contrast, impulses from both experimental and numerical data follow the same trend line, with the experimental impulse being slightly higher.

Figure 5. Force vs. Displacement of the striking mass obtained from FE results.

Figure 6. Absorbed Energy vs. Displacement obtained from FE results.

Figure 7. Comparison between experiments and finite element simulations a) Crushed distance, b) Impulse

5. CONCLUSIONS

High explosion in close range distance is simulated by using Eulerian formulation. A pressure wave is transmitted by coupling Lagrangian elements with the Eulerian and accelerates the striking mass that crushes the pultruded tube.

The underestimation of the impulse and crushed distance in finite element simulation is due to the clearing effect of the pressure wave compared to the experiment, where there is no loss of impulse because of the polystyrene disk.

In general the physical phenomenon of close range explosions can be simulated using multi-material formulations unlike with other methods, in example Conwep where close range explosions cannot be calculated. In the next stage of the present study more thorough numerical investigations will be conducted focussing on material failure and the material model, contact algorithms and blast wave propagation over a longer distance.

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